

**ПАТОМОРФОЛОГІЧНІ ОСОБЛИВОСТІ УРАЖЕННЯ ЛЕГЕНЬ ПРИ
ГЕНЕРАЛІЗОВАНОМУ КРИПТОКОКОЗИ У ПАЦІЄНТІВ З ВІЛ-
ІНФЕКЦІЄЮ / СНІД**

**PATHOMORPHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF PULMONARY INJURIES
IN GENERALIZED CRYPTOCOCCOSIS IN PATIENTS WITH HIV / AIDS**

Баран С. З., Дядик О. О., Городецька А. І., Ільченко В. В.
Baran Serhii, Dyadyk Olena, Anna Horodetska, Vladyslav Ilchenko
ORCID: 0000-0002-8839-7297

Науковий керівник: завідувачка кафедри патологічної та топографічної
анатомії НУОЗУ імені П. Л.Шупика д.мед.н. професор **Дядик О. О.**
Національний університет охорони здоров'я України імені П. Л. Шупика
Кафедра патологічної та топографічної анатомії
м. Київ, Україна
Shupyk National Healthcare University of Ukraine
Department of Pathological and Topographic Anatomy
Kyiv, Ukraine
e-mail: serhiibaran0@gmail.com

Relevance. HIV infection is one of the most acute medical and social problems, closely related to the growth of opportunistic diseases, including cryptococcosis. The frequency of respiratory lesions is more than 70% and is often associated with the generalization of the process. Diagnostic possibilities for cryptococcal lung disease in patients with HIV / AIDS remain limited due to low-specific clinical manifestations. In a significant proportion of HIV patients, cryptococcal infection is generalized with central nervous system damage, which complicates therapy and often leads to death.

Aim. To analyze and summarize the data of morphological diagnosis of lung lesions in generalized cryptococcosis, to identify the main pathomorphological features of its substrate in patients with HIV / AIDS.

Materials and methods. The study was conducted on the basis of the Kyiv City Clinical Hospital № 5 and the Department of Pathological and Topographic Anatomy of the Shupyk National Healthcare University of Ukraine. A retrospective analysis of 400 medical records of inpatients (2010-2021) was conducted and 20 cases were selected according to the inclusion criteria and protocols of pathological examinations were analyzed. Material for histopathological examination was fixed and treated by standard histological methods and stained with hematoxylin and eosin.

Results. The standard histological examination of the autopsy material revealed 20 cases of generalized cryptococcosis in patients with a laboratory-verified diagnosis of HIV / AIDS. At the clinical stage, generalized cryptococcosis was diagnosed in 16 patients, the final verification of the prevalence of the process with verification of the affected organs in all cases was performed by histological examination, and the lungs were affected in all studied cases. The pathomorphological picture of lung lesions in 13 cases is represented by pronounced alternative changes, the fungi were found in the lumens of the alveoli, vessels, and interalveolar membranes. In 7 studied cases, the granulomatous nature of the tissue inflammatory process was observed with a relatively small number of fungal druses per field of view and the predominance of encapsulated forms.

Conclusions.

The pathomorphological picture of lung lesions is polymorphic and represented by multiple foci of necrosis in some cases by an inflammatory reaction in the form of granulomatous inflammation and accumulation of cryptococci. The macroscopic picture is less specific, which necessitates not only routine histological but also histochemical diagnostic methods. The nature and severity of pathological changes depend on the state of the immune system, virulence, etiotropic therapy, as well as the duration and timeliness of diagnosis.